

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The administration of learning resources at Amando Cope College (ACC)

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Abstract

The study assessed the administration of learning resources at Amando Cope College, focusing on laboratory facilities, digital learning resources, and teaching materials. It evaluated planning, staffing, and controlling processes and analyzed differences in administration between respondents. Using a descriptive-survey method, frequency counts, percentages, and statistical tests were employed to determine the significant differences in resource management. The findings revealed that Chemistry and Anatomy laboratories, along with digital platforms like Quipper and Google Classroom, were the most utilized. Teaching materials, particularly textbooks and modules, also had high usage levels, emphasizing their importance in instructional delivery.

The level of administration of learning resources was generally high, with planning, staffing, and controlling aspects receiving strong ratings. Laboratory planning indicators, such as scientific research integration and hazardous materials management, showed high weighted means. Staffing was effective in fostering adaptive learning and technological integration, while controlling mechanisms ensured resource allocation efficiency. However, statistical analysis indicated no significant difference between teachers and students regarding the administration of learning resources. Challenges included shortages of functional laboratory equipment, bandwidth limitations affecting digital access, and insufficient teaching materials, impacting instructional effectiveness and student learning experiences.

To address these issues, the study proposed an investment plan aimed at resource improvement. Recommendations included enhancing laboratory planning, ensuring faculty training, and developing strategic institutional policies for resource control. Immediate action on identified challenges was suggested to optimize learning resource utilization. Additionally, furnishing administrative leaders with study findings could support the development of a strategic plan, improving resource management for better educational outcomes.

Keywords: Laboratory Facilities; Scientific Research; Adaptive Learning

1. Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving educational landscape, administering learning resources is more important than ever. As educational environments become increasingly diverse in terms of technology and the needs of learners in tertiary education, the role of adaptable learning resources has expanded significantly in both business and academe. These learning resources are tailored to accommodate diverse learning styles and preferences, providing every student with the opportunity to excel. Classroom lesson delivery technology, as an educational resource, is steadily becoming the standard practice nationwide across all academic levels. Also, administering learning resources in business enhances employee skills, improves productivity, and fosters innovation, leading to overall organizational growth and competitiveness.

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The quality of education also relies on the quality of the learning resources. These tools are tailored to meet the specific needs of individual learners. The Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) No. 4 of the United Nations is a commitment to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.¹ Based on this goal, education can be a transformative power to foster a sustainable and equitable world.

In today's diverse classrooms, students come from various backgrounds, have different learning styles, and may require individualized support. By being flexible and adaptable, teachers can create an inclusive and supportive learning environment where all students can thrive. Educators must recognize that each student is distinct and has varying learning requirements. Indeed, teachers need to be flexible and adaptive in their teaching style to address these needs and improve student learning.

In Asia, educational resources can vary widely. In Japan, for example, textbooks are standardized and approved by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology. These textbooks are used in public schools and cover a wide range of subjects. Also, several resources in Japan reflect a mix of traditional and modern educational tools used to support student learning.² Moreover, in South Korea, core subjects are regularly updated to reflect current educational standards, according to Asia Society 2019. Platforms like EBS or Educational Broadcasting System are used as well to offer a wide range of educational content.³ To cater to the diverse needs of students across India's varied educational landscape, textbooks are prescribed by various educational boards and state boards. Platforms also provide online courses, video lessons, and interactive exercises.⁴

Philippines has a strong support of providing quality education to all the learners by making sure that business education and workforce development are aligned to the national competency standard as stated in the Republic Act No. 10968, commonly known as the Philippine Qualifications Framework Act of 2018.⁵ In workforce development, businesses structure training programs and learning resources to meet the qualifications required for various job roles.⁶ This framework ensures that learning resources in business administration contribute to producing competent, globally competitive professionals.⁷

The Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) also adhere to the educational standards through the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) CMO 06 s. 2020; an addendum to CHED Memorandum Order No. 4 s. 2023. This order outlines strategies for sustaining flexible learning in HEIs. It also highlights the importance of accessible learning resources and support structures, ensuring that these resources are aligned with the Higher Educational Institutions' mission and goals.⁸ This requires educators to be knowledgeable about the available tools and creativity in their application, ensuring that each resource is used to its full potential.

The learning resources, whether through differentiated instruction, personalized learning paths, or the use of assistive technologies, enable educators to address the unique challenges faced by the students. That is why the learning resources provided by educational institutions should promote an inclusive learning environment where all students, regardless of their background or abilities, can thrive.

The administration of learning resources is both a challenge and an opportunity. The limited funding of private Higher Educational Institutions can hinder the ability to purchase necessary textbooks, technology, and other resources. This can affect the ability to maintain or update existing learning materials. State universities and community colleges, which are supported by the national government, have an edge in providing quality learning resources.

If provided and the schools are willing to invest, these learning resources can empower students to access and effectively utilize a diverse range of information sources. This will deepen students' understanding of complex subjects, develop skills, and ultimately achieve better academic outcomes. The Amando Cope College, established in 2004, has continued investing in learning resources since it is mandated to provide quality education to all the students. However, the changing needs of students and the opportunities available might affect the present status of the learning resources of the school. This research study was conducted to know the administration of learning resources of Amando Cope College for its 21 years of operation.

2. Conclusion

The administration of adaptable learning resources has become a cornerstone of modern educational and corporate strategies. These resources empower educators to accommodate diverse learning styles and promote inclusive, equitable learning in alignment with global commitments like Sustainable Development Goal 4. Educational systems across Asia—such as Japan's standardized textbooks, South Korea's continually updated curricula, and India's diverse educational boards—demonstrate varied yet converging approaches to quality education. In the business sector,

strategic investment in learning tools enhances employee skills and fosters innovation, even while private institutions face funding challenges. Ultimately, continued commitment to developing and managing these resources, as seen in institutions like Amando Cope College, is vital for driving both academic excellence and organizational growth.

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